

Science

A CLINICAL EFFECT OF AABHADI CHOORNA ON KATISHOOLA W.S.R. TO ASTHIMAJJAGAT VATA - A CASE STUDY

Dr. Pooja Santosh Gugale ^{*1}, Dr. Mukund .M. More ²

^{*1} M.D. (Scholar), Kaychikitsa Department, S.G.R. Ayurveda College, Solapur, India

² Ph.D (Ayurved), Kaychikitsa Department, S.G.R. Ayurveda College, Solapur, India

Abstract

Katishoola is one of the vatavyadhi and it is the commonest disorder found in clinical practice. According to Ayurveda, Katishoola is the diseases with pain in lumber region. Katishoola can be equated with low back pain .The allopathic system of medicine use non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, analgesics, which is not safe and effective for katishoola.

A 60 year old male patient had suffering from progressive pain in lower back and difficulty in bending forward over 25 ° and tingling sensation in both leg since last 12 months. X-ray of lumbo-sacral region indicated that patient was suffering from reduced L4-L5 intervertebral disc space and bony ankylosis of L4-L5 and degenerative changes in spine. He was taken modern treatment but doesn't get satisfactory relief even.

For Ayurvedic treatment he came at opd of kaychikitsa department of Seth Sakharam Nemchand Jain Ayurvedic Hospital, Solapur. He was treated for 21 days with 3 times treatment follow up. The response of the treatment was recorded and therapeutic effects were evaluated through symptomatic relief. Clinical symptoms were significantly reduced and degree of anterior flexion increased from 25° to 90 °.

This regimen is effective in successfully treating katishoola by helping to reduce the symptoms and improving the degree of anterior flexion.

Keywords: Katishoola; Low Back Pain; Aabhadi Choorna; Asti-Majjagat Vata.

Cite This Article: Dr. Pooja Santosh Gugale, and Dr. Mukund .M. More. (2018). “A CLINICAL EFFECT OF AABHADI CHOORNA ON KATISHOOLA W.S.R. TO ASTHIMAJJAGAT VATA - A CASE STUDY.” *International Journal of Research - Granthaalayah*, 6(3), 172-175. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1213600>.

1. Introduction

Katishoola is a disease which is mainly caused by vitiation of *vata dosha*. A successful life of every individual is greater depend upon locomotion i.e. ability of using joints and bones. *Katishoola* cripples the freedom of movements.

The 2010 global burden of disease study has estimated that low back pain is one of the top ten disease. It is difficult to estimate the incidence of low back pain (*Katishoola*) as now a days the incidence of first episode is by the early adulthood and symptom tend to recur overtime.

In Ayurveda, *Katishoola* has not been described as individual disease. *Katishoola* has been denoted by different terms in *nanatmaj vata vyadhis* as *katigraha*, *shronibheda*, *trikgraha* ⁽¹⁾. *Kati* is one of the region of *vata-dosh* ⁽²⁾ and *vata-dosh* is responsible for *katishoola*. While describing *sandhishoola* in Ayurvedic texts it is clearly mentioned that “*Sandhishoola*” ⁽³⁾ is one of the symptom of “*Asthimajjagata vata*” ⁽⁴⁾. Laying special emphasis on this particular *lakshana* we have chosen *katisandhi* as a reference for this study. Common cause of *Katishoola* (low back pain) include lumbar strain, nerve irritation, lumbar radiculopathy, etc.

Aabhadi choorna contains mainly *Vatshamak dravyas* and also having properties of *Balya*, *Deepan*, *Pachan* and *Asthisandhankar*. This combination may help in *sampraptibhanga* of *Asthimajjagata vata* and hence relieve *katishoola*.

1.1. Case Report

A 60 year old man, who attended the Outdoor Patients Department of S.S.N.J. Ayurved Hospital, Solapur for treatment of his lower back pain was selected and admitted to the ward. He had a 12 month history of progressively increasing pain in lower back and both buttocks and tingling sensation in both legs. He was an otherwise healthy farmer, capable of doing heavy work. He had no history of trauma and his symptoms have increased gradually.

On physical examination, patient had little discomfort in buttocks on turning to the lateral side. Straight leg raising test was negative in both legs. He could flex the body forward up to 25 °. Motor and sensory functions were normal in right and left legs and both deep and superficial reflexes were also normal.

All details of the patient including present history, past history, treatment history, dietary habits, lifestyle and addictions were recorded before the treatment. Necessary examinations and X-ray in lumbo sacral region were done and findings were recorded. Patient was kept on a normal diet without any specific restrictions and was advised not to lift any weights. The patient was treated with *Aabhadi choorna* for 21 days.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials

Aushadhi yoga: - **AABHADI CHOORNA** ⁽⁵⁾

Table 1 : Showing contains of Aabhadi choorna

SR.NO.	DRUG	FORM	
1	Aabha	Choorna	Same quantity
2	Rasna	Choorna	
3	Guduchi	Choorna	
4	Shatavari	Choorna	
6.	Shatapushpa	Choorna	
7.	Ashwagandha	Choorna	
8	Hapusha	Choorna	
9	Vrudhhadaru	Choorna	
10	Yavani	Choorna	
11	Ajamoda	Choorna	

Choorna Nirman Vidhi ⁽⁶⁾

The raw material in choorna form will be collected from S.S.N.J. Ayurved *Aoushadhalaya* Trust's Ayurved Rasashala (ISO certified company) of Particles size of 80-100 mesh. All dravya will be taken as per the proportion mentioned in above chart. They will mix with the help of *khalva yantra*. Phytochemical analysis of thus prepared choorna will be done before use.

Dose : 4gm × twice in a day.
 Anupan : *Koshnajala*
 Aushadhi-Sevan Kala : *Adhobhakt (Vyan Udan kala)*
 Route of Administration : Oral.
 Duration : 21 days.
 Follow up : After every 7 days

2.2. Methods

Center of study: S.S.N.J.Ayurved Rughnalya, solapur.

Method of sampling: simple randomized.

3. Observation

Response to the treatment was recorded and therapeutic effects were evaluated by symptomatic relief of the patient. It was observed that the patient's clinical symptoms were reduced gradually during the treatment period and degree of anterior flexion increased from 25 ° to 90°.

Table 2 : Showing Evaluation of clinical symptoms

SYMPTOMS	BEFORE TREATMENT	AFTER TREATMENT
Pain in low back	Grade 4	Grade 1
Pain in both buttocks	Grade 3	Grade 0
Tingling sensation	Grade 3	Grade 1
Degree of anterior flexion	25°	90°

4. Discussion

- **Discussion on vhaydhi:** According to the Ayurveda, *shoola* (pain) occurs due to vitiation of *vata dosha* ⁽⁷⁾. *Vata Dosha* is vitiated by *srotas awarodata* (obstruction of channels) and *Dhatu kshaya* (depletion of tissues/ malnutrition). In *kati-shoola*, *Apana vata* is mainly involved. So, the aim of the treatment is to pacify vitiated *vata dosha* especially *Apana vata*.
- **Discussion on Aushadhi yoga:** Ingredients of *Aabhadi choorna* have the properties of *Vatashamaka* (Pacify the vitiated *vata dosha*), *Vedana sthapana* (Sedative), *Shoola Prashamana* (Analgesic), *Balya* (Promote strength), *Rasayana* (Rejuvenation), *Asthisandhankar* (Improving qualities of bones and reformation of wasting tissues). As the drugs used in the present study have above properties, they are beneficial for diseases originated by vitiation of *vata dosha*. Patient suffering from *kati shoola* showed a significant symptomatic relief with this treatment regimen.

5. Result

With use of *Abhadi choorna* all symptoms of *katishool* reduce and improving the degree of anterior flexion.

6. Conclusion

It is concluded that this treatment regimen completely or partially relieves the symptoms in *katishoola*. This medicine can be utilized in treating patients who are suffering from *katishoola* to reduce both signs and symptoms successfully and with greater effectiveness. It is proposed that the therapy may be accepted as a treatment method of *katishoola*.

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*Corresponding author.

E-mail address: poojagugale14@ gmail.com/mukundmore@ yahoo.in